

Association between Low to High-Density Lipoprotein Ratio and Renal Function in Elderly Hypertensives in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Recent evidence indicates that serum lipids, apart from hypertension, may potentially hasten the deterioration of renal function.

Aim: The aim of this study is to investigate the association between low to high-density lipoprotein ratio and renal function in elderly hypertensive patients in a tertiary care hospital.

Hypothesis: We hypothesize that a higher low to high-density lipoprotein ratio is associated with worse renal function in elderly hypertensive patients in a tertiary care hospital.

Results: During the investigation, renal function declined by an average of 3 percent; hypertension accelerated this decline. Individuals whose low-to-high-density lipoprotein cholesterol ratio was greater than 4.5 experienced a 30% more rapid decline in cholesterol levels than those whose ratio was below 3.5. Statistical analyses revealed, both the contribution of the lipoprotein ratio and the protective effect of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol alone remained significant. The contribution of lipids to the investigation of joint effects was limited to participants who experienced concurrent increases in blood pressure and lipid levels.

Conclusion: The findings indicate that blood lipids, apart from hypertension, exert an influence on the deterioration of renal function.

Keywords: Elderly Hypertension, Low-Density Lipoprotein, High-Density Lipoprotein, Low To High-Density Lipoprotein Ratio, Renal Function, Treatment Strategies.

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Introduction

Elderly hypertension is a prevalent condition that increases the risk of cardiovascular disease and renal impairment. Understanding the association between lipid levels and renal function in elderly hypertensive patients is crucial for developing effective prevention and treatment strategies. Previous studies have reported conflicting results regarding the relationship between lipid levels and renal function in hypertensive patients.

There is a lack of research examining the association between low to high-density lipoprotein ratio and renal function in elderly hypertensive patients in a tertiary care hospital setting. This study rationale was to address the knowledge gap by investigating the association between low to high-density lipoprotein ratio and renal function in elderly hypertensive patients in a tertiary care hospital. The research question is what is the association between low to high-density lipoprotein ratio and renal function in elderly hypertensive patients in a tertiary care hospital? The aim of this

study is to investigate the association between low to high-density lipoprotein ratio and renal function in elderly hypertensive patients in a tertiary care hospital. We hypothesize that a higher low to high-density lipoprotein ratio is associated with worse renal function in elderly hypertensive patients in a tertiary care hospital.

Materials & Methods

The study was conducted only after obtaining permission from the Institution Ethics Committee. This study was conducted by the Department of Medicine at Government Medical College & Hospital, Sundargarh. The current study included 100 patients with dyslipidemia. To be eligible, patients had to have dyslipidemia, defined as non-HDL-C levels of < 40 mg/dl at two consecutive screening exams, and be free of coronary heart disease or any other serious illness.

However, hypertension and type II diabetes were not considered reasons for exclusion. The lipid

acceptance criteria picked patients from the higher end of the range for serum total cholesterol. The range for HDL-C was similar between the people in the study and the people who were screened. We also excluded 29 participants who had abnormal laboratory safety markers (hemoglobin, leukocyte count, aspartate aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase, bilirubin, and creatinine). Although the top limit for serum creatinine was 1.50 mg/dl were included in the study.

In the study, nurses took blood pressure measurements with calibrated mercury sphygmomanometers. We made the recordings with the subjects seated after the interviews and before collecting the blood sample. The cuff measured 12×40 cm, and diastolic pressure was defined using Korotkoff phase V (phase IV is when sounds can be heard till the end of the scale). We took all measurements at 5-mmHg intervals. We measured lipid levels and performed semiannual determinations of major safety markers, such as aspartate aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase, bilirubin, and creatinine, using standard in-house analytic techniques and an automated multichannel laboratory suite. We determined the creatinine levels using Jaffe's technique.

Statistical Methods

We analyzed the mean levels of lipids, blood pressure, and other factors, including serum creatinine. We determined the cross-sectional associations between serum creatinine levels and other variables using Pearson's correlation coefficients. We estimated the decline in renal function for each individual using the least-squares linear regression slope based on creatinine determinations. The Statistical Analysis System (SAS) evaluated the contribution of independent variables to the change in serum creatinine using multiple linear regression models with either baseline or in-trial levels. We used ANOVA to compare the mean creatinine changes between different subgroups.

Results

There were no significant cross-sectional relationships between measured serum creatinine and blood pressure or lipoprotein values (HDL-C, LDL-C, and triglycerides). The associations between creatinine and relative weight (BMI; kilograms divided by meters squared) or body weight (kg) were highly significant, but the coefficients were only +.05 and +.09, respectively.

Age did not affect the pace of loss in renal function, with mean creatinine changes of 0.6, 0.7, and 0.8 mg/dl in the age groups of 40–44, 45–49, and 50–55 years, respectively ($P = \text{NS}$). Neither smoking nor physical activity had a significant impact on the creatinine change. The association between the creatinine level was an inverse one, and the change

was more than twofold in participants with creatinine less than 1.6 mg/dl compared to those with baseline levels larger than 2.1 mg/dl. Hypertension increased the deterioration in renal function. When considering Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP), the fastest drop, 7.5 ± 8.1 mm/Hg, was in the highest quintile, with MAP greater than or equal to 112 mm Hg; the mean decline in the lowest quintile, with MAP less than 98 mm Hg, was 6.9 ± 7.8 mm/Hg. When the systolic blood pressure was less than 140 mm Hg, the mean creatinine change was 2.1 ± 1.2 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ in normotensive patients and 1.4 ± 0.9 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ in treated hypertensive subjects ($P < 0.05$). In either therapy group, no relationship was found between mean in-trial LDL-C or triglyceride levels and the rate of decrease in renal function. In contrast, HDL-C levels had a negative contribution, with the biggest mean changes in both treatment groups when HDL-C was low and the smallest when HDL-C was high (45 mg/dl). The LDL-C/HDL-C ratio had a big effect on the rate of decline.

Hypertensive participants (diastolic BP >95 mm Hg) with an LDL-C/HDL-C ratio greater than 4.5 had significantly higher blood creatinine levels ($P < .01$) compared to normotensive subjects with a low lipoprotein ratio or hypertensive subjects with normal lipids. In analyses with HDL-C as the lipid variable, the difference was not statistically significant. The effect of hypertension on the deterioration in renal function was independent of lipid levels.

Discussion

Our findings, consistent with prior research, suggest that hypertension is one of the factors driving the rate of decline in renal function, even in people without renal disease. However, as far as we know, this is the human study to demonstrate a link between declining renal function and serum lipids.

In Western nations, the decline of kidney function with age is considered a "physiological" process [8]. It is believed that the decline happens regardless of blood pressure or diets rich in protein [9,10], but arterial hypertension speeds up the decline. The rate of deterioration varies according to race and gender [5]. Renal function measurement is challenging in community studies, with all methods established for clinical use in patients with increasing renal failure. Endogenous creatinine clearance is close to glomerular filtration rate, but there is a consistent negative relationship between serum creatinine concentration and endogenous creatinine clearance, as long as the volume of urine doesn't change in a regular way. With these conditions met [11], a linear decrease in the reciprocals of serum creatinine can be used to infer the decline in glomerular filtration rate, a direct indicator of renal function [5-7]. Our study population showed a reg-

ular distribution of creatinine change, with around 30% of individuals experiencing a decrease or no change. Other populations have shown a similar distribution trend for creatinine change [12]. Our findings regarding joint impacts are based on this assumption. The existing literature lacks relevant comparative data. The cholesterol acceptance threshold likely contributed to LDL-C's lack of significance. This criterion selected patients at the upper end of the total, resulting in LDL-C distributions. Triglycerides, either alone or in combination with other lipids and/or hypertension, had no connection with creatinine alteration. This is rather surprising, given the strong relationship between triglycerides and HDL-C, as well as triglycerides and hypertension in the setting of the insulin resistance syndrome [12].

How might lipids contribute to the decline in renal function? Dyslipidemia, among other things, causes glomerular damage, which leads to glomerulosclerosis, according to the core pathophysiological concept [13,14]. Experimental data supports this hypothesis, and some have even proposed a shared pathophysiological background between glomerulosclerosis and atherosclerosis [6]. Human mesangial cells, which look like changed smooth muscle cells, take up native LDL and apolipoprotein E-containing lipoproteins through a process involving receptors. In vitro, glomerular epithelial cells also express lipoprotein receptors [5]. Although the kidney has a role in apolipoprotein A-I degradation, only indirect evidence of HDL-C involvement is available. Rare metabolic illnesses associated with low HDL-C, such as lecithin-cholesterol acyltransferase deficiency, have reported glomerular lipid deposits [15]. However, an exact mechanism by which glomerulosclerosis could lead to reduced creatinine clearance is so far unresolved.

Because hypertension is one of the major risk factors for end-stage renal failure, researchers have mostly studied the deterioration in renal function with age in relation to BP levels. Our data confirm the contribution of elevated BP to the decline in renal function. However, we only detected the effect of elevated systolic BP (>160 mm Hg), which aligns with the Baltimore Longitudinal Studies on Aging [16-18]. With regard to diastolic BP, there was a classic dose-response pattern. In multiple regression analyses, the contribution of diastolic BP remained statistically significant, but studies of the joint effects revealed a significant interdependence between diastolic BP and the LDL-C/HDL-C ratio in the decline of renal function. The joint effect of hypertension and HDL-C exhibited a largely similar pattern. One possible explanation for these results is that high blood pressure is the main cause, and the lipids act in a way that fits with the lipid hypothesis, with HDL playing a key role in reverse cholesterol transport.

The study of serum creatinine and its change over time encounters some methodological issues. A major issue is the large interindividual and intraindividual variations. This offers, in addition to the relatively narrow age range, a partial explanation for why we were not able to demonstrate any cross-sectional association between age and creatinine. A second problem arises from the close correlation between the initial value and the change, an association partly explained by "regression toward the mean." In our study cohort, using linear regression slopes to estimate initial and final creatinine values did not eliminate this association, leaving the possibility of a true effect. However, our data is insufficient to support further speculation.

In addition to the methodological problems discussed above, our study has other shortcomings and restrictions. This was a post hoc analysis in a study population of white men, and the results may not be applicable to other races or women. Second, the population included dyslipidemic, primarily hypercholesterolemic subjects, and the lipid acceptance criterion's slight variation decreased the relative contributions of LDL-C, the primary cholesterol carrier in the human body. On the other hand, initial screening excluded subjects with renal disease, and continuous patient monitoring ensured the reliability of both laboratory and clinical data.

Conclusion

This study's outcomes suggest that the LDL-HDL ratio plays a significant role in the development of renal failure in elderly hypertensive individuals. The findings indicate that blood lipids, in addition to hypertension, affect the decline in renal function. Further research could examine the potential therapeutic benefits of lowering the LDL-HDL ratio in preventing or delaying renal impairment in elderly hypertension patients.

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